

A Study of Tukarama's Select Translated Poetry

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18775776

Introduction:

This research paper deals with the various English translations of Tukarama's poetry, beginning with the pioneering work of Christian missionaries and extending to the modern poets and thinkers. The study focuses on how different translators, ranging from missionaries like Nelson Frazer and K. B. Marathe to literary figures such as Dilip Chitre and Arun Kolatkar. Saint Tukarama is considered a luminary among the saints of Maharashtra. Saint Namdeva and Saint Dnyaneshwara laid the foundation of the Varkari sect. Tukarama (1608–1649), one of the greatest exponents of the Varkari Bhakti tradition of Maharashtra, occupies a towering position in this literary and spiritual landscape. His poetry,

composed in simple yet deeply moving Marathi *Abhangas*, continues to inspire generations with its universal values of devotion (bhakti), humility, truth, equality, and spiritual yearning.

Keywords: Translations, Missionaries, Saints, Poetry, Abhangas, Varkari.

The first full-length English translation of Tukarama's *Abhangas* was undertaken by Reverent J. Nelson Fraser in collaboration with K. B. Marathe, under the title *The Poems of Tukarama* (published by the Christian Literature Society in 1909). This translation emerged not purely from aesthetic or spiritual curiosity but from the missionary zeal to present Tukarama's thought within a Christian framework.

**When you have kept the principal, why need you care about interest !
Seal up your own bundle at home; you cannot avoid the attempts of the
strangers. Robbers will assault you not far on the road; your business
takes you through the swindlers' quarter. Tuka says, Appearances are
all false; secret wiles will catch you. ¹**

The *abhangas* by Saint Tukarama reveals that if capital is preserved, then only profit is easily possible. We should keep devotion as a treasure in the heart-temple, safeguard it, and hold it close. Be aware of the

enemy in the form of desires. Tuka says it is false to pretend outwardly while keeping hypocrisy within. This *abhangas* highlights the futility of outward charity and superficial good deeds when the heart remains impure. He warns that pride

over small gains and the bondage of hypocrisy nullify true spiritual progress. Tukarama emphasises that sincerity, inner purity, and honesty matter more than external show, reminding seekers that without cleansing the self within, all rituals and actions are hollow. Translation has always been a powerful medium for transmitting philosophical, spiritual, and literary traditions across cultures. Saint Tukarama, one of the greatest Varkari saints of Maharashtra, occupies a distinctive position in the Bhakti tradition through his *Abhangas*, poetic utterances that combine devotion, philosophy, and social reform. While Tukarama's language is steeped in colloquial Marathi, the universality of his spiritual experience has attracted translators across centuries.

In the twentieth century, literary translators such as Dilip Chitre and Arun Kolatkar gave Tukarama a new life in world literature. Chitre's *Says Tuka* is widely acclaimed for its combination of fidelity and creativity. Chitre recognized the impossibility of transferring Tukarama's exact idiom into English, but he compensated by crafting versions that captured the saint's immediacy, irony, and passionate

devotion. For instance, Chitre employed crisp, colloquial English to parallel Tukarama's rustic Marathi, ensuring that the translations did not sound ornamental or artificially archaic. Arun Kolatkar, on the other hand, experimented with modernist techniques, aligning Tukarama with contemporary global poetic trends and highlighting his rebellious, anti-establishment voice. Both these translators brought Tukarama closer to international literary readerships,

Critically, Chitre's translations succeed where Fraser & Marathe often fell short: by balancing fidelity with literary imagination, he conveys not only the philosophical and devotional content of Tukarama's *abhangas* but also the cultural, social, and poetic texture of the Marathi originals. His work demonstrates that translation can be a creative, interpretive act that honors both the meaning and the form, rhythm, and voice of the source text. In this sense, *Says Tuka* allows contemporary readers to experience Tukarama as both a mystic and a social reformer, maintaining the vitality, immediacy, and musicality of his *abhangas*, while still speaking compellingly in English.

Have I utterly lost my hold on reality to imagine myself writing poetry? I am sure your illustrious devotees, all famous poets, will laugh at me. Today, I face the toughest test of life: Whereof I have no experience, thereof I have been asked to sing. I am the innocent one asked to sin, without any foretaste of what I must commit I am just a beginner, untutored in the art; My Master Himself is unrevealed to me. Illuminate, and inspire me, O Lord. Says Tuka, my time is running out.²

The above *abhangas* exemplifies Tukarama's humility, spiritual insecurity and profound devotion while highlighting the existential and poetic anxieties of a novice poet-saint confronting divine inspiration. In the original Marathi, Tukarama often begins verses with a self-deprecatory tone, expressing feelings

of inadequacy and unworthiness (*mi shikshak naahi, mi navin aahe* "I am untutored, a beginner"), especially in relation to spiritual or poetic responsibility. The idea of being "asked to sing that which I have no experience of reflects a core bhakti tension: the devotee must articulate the ineffable, singing praise of a Lord whose

nature remains partly hidden (*majha prabhu adnyat*). The abhangas carry layered meanings: at one level, the saint expresses personal doubt and humility; at another, he acknowledges the immediacy and inevitability of devotional duty, urging God for illumination. The original rhythm and repetition, common in Marathi abhangas, create a meditative cadence, while the stark self-doubt conveys both intimacy and vulnerability.

Conclusion:

Saint Tukarama, one of the foremost saints of the Marathi bhakti tradition, composed thousands of *abhangas*-short, lyrical devotional poems that celebrate the divine, critique social and ritual hypocrisy, and articulate the moral, ethical, and spiritual concerns of the common people. His poetry, composed in the vernacular Marathi of the seventeenth century, blends

devotional intensity, folk idiom, and metaphysical reflection. Translating such poetry into English, therefore, involves not only linguistic conversion but also the careful mediation of cultural, philosophical, and poetic nuances. The said research paper critically examines the translations of Tukarama's abhangas, focusing on two landmark works: *The Poems of Tukarama* by Nelson Fraser and K. B. Marathe, *Says Tuka* by Dilip Chitre.

References:

1. Fraser, J. Nelson and Marathe, K. B, trans. *The Poems of Tukarama I*. Delhi: MLBD,2007, p.314.
2. Chitre, Dilip, trans. *Says Tuka-1: Selected Poems of Tukaram*. Pune: Penguin Classics,1991, p.06.